

AE4EU

Agroecology for Europe (AE4EU)

Towards the development of agroecology in Europe

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Summary

Two policy briefs are included in this deliverable.

Improving Eco-Schemes in the Light of Agroecology: Key Recommendations for the 2023-2027 Common Agricultural Policy discusses the new CAP structure, as well as its content, and provides recommendations how to improve the eco-schemes. They are for the first time the main stated body that the Commission has chosen to bring forward agroecology. The policy brief was written and released during a time when the Member States and Commission were still in conversation on what would be included in the country's Strategic Plans, a process which has now almost ended. The recommendations include advancing agroecological practices; creating basic premiums for eco-friendly agricultural production systems; structuring multi-dimensional eco-schemes that encourage the implementation of multiple practices at once; ensuring the proportionality between the level of payment and the expected environmental benefits; maintaining rigorous conditionality by not paying for what should be mandatory; and using public money for public goods. The brief ends with an assessment on which countries have included agroecology in their plans, as well as which schemes seem promising or concerning for the advancement of agroecology.

10 Steps to Achieve the European Green Deal takes the time to show that many of the targets found within the European Green Deal, including the Farm to Fork and Biodiversity Strategies, can be met by a transition to agroecology. It discusses the lack of roadmap that exists within many European legislations and aims to provide such a map through 10 concrete steps that can be taken to achieve no net emissions of greenhouse gases within the agricultural sector. These steps aim to provide a framework to achieve the promised reduction of chemical pesticides, fertilisers, nutrient losses, and environmental and climate footprints; protection of EU's protected areas; planting of 3 billion trees; restoration of high diversity landscape features; and expansion of organic farming.

1. Introduction

Policy briefs are a key instrument for CSA projects such as AE4EU, as they allow the project to share with policy makers and a larger audience insights that are gathered from all other work packages. For this reason, we have chosen to devote our first two policy briefs on recommendations both for the Common Agricultural Policy and the European Green Deal, through a wide lens. These are just the first two of the planned briefs, with the others devoting themselves to a more acute lens, focusing on topics

such as financing, living labs and research infrastructure. These policy briefs are a direct way to contribute for AE4EU to the design and development of the partnership on agroecology living labs and research infrastructure, as well as the general development of agroecology in Europe.

2. Policy brief n°1

Improving Eco-schemes in the Light of Agroecology

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Key recommendations for the 2023-2027 Common Agricultural Policy

On the 25th of June 2021, the EU finalised its negotiations for the new Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) that is set to come into power on the 1 January 2023 and run until 2027. While this CAP is being championed by its creators as a radical new framework for tackling agricultural and environmental issues, it has left many civil society organisations to wonder if it will deliver on the commitments found in other legislations such as the Farm to Fork Strategy of the EU Green Deal.

The Horizon 2020 project, Agroecology for Europe (AE4EU), aims to take part in this discussion and provide insights for policy makers and Member States in order to ensure that this new CAP is as robust as possible and delivers on its promises for change. One of AE4EU's primary missions is to also support the preparation of the European R&I partnership on agroecology living labs and research infrastructures.

Integrating Eco-schemes according to agroecology

One of principal changes within the new CAP has been the inclusion of Eco-schemes – voluntary programmes linked to the first pillar which will be available to farmers with the hope to incentivize more ecological and environmentally-friendly farming practices. While agroecology holds an eminent space within this list by being listed as one of the primary recommendations, it does so within a role of just another practice to achieve a more sustainable farming system.

As stated by many before, such as Hill (1985), Gliessman (2016) and Agroecology Europe (2021), agroecology is not just the substitution of one practice for another, it is a restructuring of the entire agricultural and food system. It is not just a tool to increase efficiency, it is a paradigm shift that uses food, health and the environment as a starting point to create a system that is inherently resilient. Further, it is important to remember that agroecology consists of three major elements: *a set of practices, a science and a social movement* (Wezel et al., 2009, Agroecology Europe, 2020).

As Agroecology Europe (2021) has proposed earlier this year, it is important to separate practices (i.e. buffer strips, winter cover crops) and production systems (i.e. agroecology, agroforestry, organic farming) for a more cohesive integration of Eco-schemes. Production systems such as conservation agriculture, agroforestry, and extensive silvo-pastoral systems should be subsidized by basic premiums, as organic farming is. Practices that can be implemented on their own, and are not production systems themselves, should be reclassified into three separate measures, those that: increase input efficiency, substitute inputs and redesign the production system. Such categories can be further classified according to the function they fulfil within agroecosystems: soil fertility, weed management, pest and disease control, pasture management, animal welfare, biodiversity and pollinator conservation, and climate change mitigation and adaptation. A further description of what such a system would look like can be seen in Table 1, where each measure is represented by a different colour: efficiency (E) in orange, substitution (S) in blue, and redesign (R) in green.

Table 1: Classification of the Eco-schemes proposed by the Commission according to the logic of "efficiency – substitution – redesign" (letter and colour code) and the logic of classification of measures in relation to agroecosystem service management (columns). Each measure is represented by a different colour: efficiency (E) in orange, substitution (S) in blue, and redesign (R) in green. (source: Agroecology Europe 2021).

	MANAGEMENT OF ALL TYPES OF CROPS AND GRASSLANDS		MANAGEMENT OF ALL TYPES OF CROPS		GRASSLANDS AND LIVESTOCK		ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT		
	Soil fertility	Weed management	Pest management	Disease management	Grassland management	Animal welfare	Biodiversity conservation and restoration	Pollination conservation and enhancement	Climate mitigation and adaptation
IPM Practices									
Buffer strips with management practices and without pesticide			R				R	R	R
Mechanical weed control		S			S				
Increased use of resilient, pest-resistant crop varieties and species	R	R	R	R					R
Land lying fallow with species composition for biodiversity purpose							R	R	
Agroecological practices									
Crop rotation with leguminous crops	R	R	R	R			R	R	R
Mixed cropping - multi cropping	R	R	R	R			R	R	R
Cover crop between tree rows on permanent crops	R	R	R	R			R	R	R
Winter soil cover and catch crops above conditionality	R	R	R	R					R
Low input efficient grass-based livestock system	R	R			R	R	R		R
Mixed species/diverse sward of permanent grassland for biodiversity purpose			R	R	R	R	R	R	R
Improved rice cultivation to decrease methane emissions									E
Husbandry and animal welfare plans									
Providing access to pastures and increasing grazing period for grazing					R	R			
Shepherding on open spaces and between permanent crops, transhumance		R			R	R	R		R
Semi-natural habitat creation and enhancement		R	R	R			R	R	R
Establishment and maintenance of permanent grassland	R				R	R	R	R	R
Extensive use of permanent grassland	R		R		R	R	R	R	R
Animal health prevention and control plans: overall plan for reducing the risk of					R	R			R
Practices increasing animal robustness, fertility, longevity and adaptability,					R	R			R
Mixed grazing (minimum 2 species)					R	R			
Improved manure management and storage	R				R				
Carbon farming practices									
Rewetting wetlands/peatlands, paludiculture							R		R
Minimum water table level during winter									R
Appropriate management of residues, i.e. seeding on residues	R						R		R
Nutrients management plan, use of innovative approaches to minimise	E								E
Precision farming									
Precision crop farming to reduce inputs (fertilisers, water, plant protection)	E	E	E	E					E
Improving irrigation efficiency	E	E	E	E					E
Managing crop water demand (switching to less water intensive crops,									R
Feed additives to decrease emissions from enteric fermentation									E
Other practices									
Erosion prevention strips and wind breaks	R						R	R	R
Establishment or maintenance of terraces and strip cropping	R	R	R	R			R		
Implementation of nitrates-related measures	E				E				E

Further, in order for Eco-schemes to truly lead to a long-term redesign of agricultural systems, it is important for them to be multi-dimensional. Policy makers should encourage the implementation of several practices at once, as a practice on its own has little strength in creating true sustainability. Rather than a menu of options farmers can choose from, packages should be constructed in a way where complexity and synergy is created on farms with many proven environmental benefits. Higher subsidies can also be given to farmers who are implementing these packages or several practices at once - Agroecology Europe has provided calculations of what this would look like (Agroecology Europe, 2021). Such packages could also include multiple tiers, with different levels of pay for different efforts, rather than flat rates (BirdLife Europe et al., 2021).

It also important for conditionality to remain rigorous, and not be weakened or included within Eco-schemes. Practices that are already common or very basic should not be rewarded. For example, a few countries are planning to pay farmers to grow cover crops during winter. Although this practice is vital for the protection of soils, there are already obligations to have soil cover during sensitive periods within conditionality. Funding should focus on demanding interventions that maintain fair rewards for farmers who want to make greater efforts to be more sustainable and provide ecosystem services. If successful funding schemes are not created, there is immense risk that low ambition schemes will sideline more worthwhile schemes which will not be attractive enough for farmers to uptake them on a large scale (BirdLife Europe et al., 2021).

Around 25% of the CAP direct payments, € 8-9 billion per year are planned to go to Eco-schemes. This *public taxpayer money*, along with the total €387 billion CAP budget, should pay for *public goods* and reward ecosystem services with proven environmental benefits, for example the carbon sequestration in agricultural soils, restoration of biodiversity farms and in agricultural landscapes, the development of ecological networks and conservation of semi-natural landscape elements (e.g. hedges, wood clumps, herbaceous strips, ponds).

Recommendations for Eco-schemes

1. Separate practices from production systems.
2. Create basic premiums for all eco-friendly agricultural production systems.
3. Create multi-dimensional Eco-schemes that encourage the implementation of multiple practices at once.
4. Ensure proportionality between the level of payment and the expected environmental benefits.
5. Maintain rigorous conditionality and do not reward practices that maintain the status quo - do not pay for what should be mandatory.
6. Public money for public goods.

Assessment of draft Eco-schemes

An assessment of the Eco-schemes shows that only 19 % of schemes are likely to deliver their environmental objectives, with 40 % needing significant improvements and 41% either concerning or completely greenwashing. Well-designed schemes are underfunded, while their less demanding counterparts remain more financially attractive (BirdLife Europe et al., 2021). This is dangerous for true environmental benefits to biodiversity, soil health, and climate mitigation and adaptation.

Further, the forementioned assessment has found many policy gaps within the proposed Strategic Plans including only two countries creating schemes to reduce antimicrobial use (although both schemes were deemed poor and as potential hidden subsidies for intensive animal farming); only one scheme reducing herd size; only a few schemes focusing on growing feed to reduce feed import (a major solution for climate mitigation); only one scheme ceasing farming on drained peatlands (another major source of climate mitigation) and none to incentivize paludiculture; half of the schemes targeted reduction of pesticide use; minimal support for agroforestry; and finally, the inclusion of precision farming without any rules for the reduction in inputs, especially fertiliser and pesticide use (BirdLife Europe et al., 2021).

Agroecology related Eco-schemes in draft national CAP strategic plans

An analysis by the AE4EU project on the inclusion of agroecology related Eco-schemes in the draft national strategic plans, shows a low number of agroecology-related policies (Table 2). While on average, countries have around three Eco-schemes related to agroecology, with five being the highest (Poland) and zero the lowest (Cyprus), there is a lot to be said for the strength of the existing Eco-schemes, which as mentioned above, are found by many civil society organisations as poor and unlikely to deliver on environmental benefits. The most popular Eco-schemes in the Strategic Plans are extensive grasslands management, use of cover/catch crops and organic farming. The least popular, with no schemes found in any countries, are “mixed cropping - multi cropping” and “improved rice cultivation to decrease methane emissions” (although Spain does mention rice production in one of their schemes, the scope remains unclear). Multidimensional Eco-schemes are the most likely to deliver, nevertheless they are found only in five countries - Czech Republic, Estonia, Latvia, Slovakia and the Netherlands. Interestingly, while the Netherlands has only chosen to include a single Eco-scheme within its Strategic Plan, there are nevertheless four different agroecological elements found in the scheme.

Country	Number of Eco-schemes	Eco-scheme name
Austria	3	Cover crop between permanent crops Low intensity grass-based livestock system Winter soil cover and catch crops
Belgium (Flanders)	3	Crop rotation with leguminous crops Low intensity grass-based livestock system Organic practices and standards
Belgium (Wallonia)	3	Winter soil cover and catch crops Low intensity grass-based livestock system Permanent grassland for biodiversity
Bulgaria	4	Winter soil cover and catch crops Cover crop between permanent crops Permanent grassland for biodiversity Organic practices and standards
Croatia	3	Permanent grassland for biodiversity Winter soil cover and catch crops Crop rotation with leguminous crops
Czech Republic	2	Winter soil cover and catch crops Permanent grassland for biodiversity
Cyprus	0	
Denmark	3	Winter soil cover and catch crops Permanent grassland for biodiversity Organic practices and standards
Estonia	2	Crop rotation with leguminous crops Organic practices and standards
Finland	4	Low intensity grass-based livestock system Permanent grassland for biodiversity Crop rotation with leguminous crops Winter soil cover and catch crops
France	4	Permanent grassland for biodiversity Organic practices and standards Crop rotation with leguminous crops Cover crop between permanent crops
Germany	3	Low intensity grass-based livestock system Permanent grassland for biodiversity Crop rotation with leguminous crops
Greece	3	Use of crops/plant varieties more resilient to climate change Permanent grassland for biodiversity Organic practices and standards
Hungary	3	Permanent grassland for biodiversity Low intensity grass-based livestock system Organic practices and standards
Ireland	2	Low intensity grass-based livestock system Permanent grassland for biodiversity
Italy	3	Permanent grassland for biodiversity Cover crop between permanent crops Crop rotation with leguminous crops
Latvia	4	Winter soil cover and catch crops Cover crop between permanent crops Crop rotation with leguminous crops Low intensity grass-based livestock system
Netherlands	4	Permanent grassland for biodiversity Organic practices and standards Crop rotation with leguminous crops Winter soil cover and catch crops
Poland	5	Permanent grassland for biodiversity Organic practices and standards Crop rotation with leguminous crops Winter soil cover and catch crops Low intensity grass-based livestock system
Portugal	2	Permanent grassland for biodiversity Organic practices and standards
Slovakia	1	Permanent grassland for biodiversity
Slovenia	3	Winter soil cover and catch crops Permanent grassland for biodiversity Cover crop between permanent crops
Spain	4	Crop rotation with leguminous crops Cover crop between permanent crops Low intensity grass-based livestock system Permanent grassland for biodiversity
Sweden	3	Organic practices and standards Permanent grassland for biodiversity Winter soil cover and catch crops

The way forward

It is clear that many Eco-schemes have not been created with enough coherence, some barely going beyond basic practices and conditionality, and unlikely to sufficiently deliver on needed ecosystem services. **What are needed are multi-dimensional Eco-schemes with robust funding, clear targets and proven benefits in order to improve the sustainability of farming in Europe.**

When it comes to the overall structure of the CAP, **our final recommendation is for all subsidies that support hectares and livestock heads to be phased out and replaced with basic agricultural incomes per full-time equivalent worker**, which would directly support small-scale and family farmers, employment in agriculture and facilitate the much-needed generational renewal in the sector.

The formal review process by the European Commission of the national CAP strategic plans is taking place in early 2022 and marks a key milestone to pave the way towards a consistent agricultural policy **that is beneficial to the climate, biodiversity and health**. The Commission should encourage and support Member States to restructure their draft national Strategic Plans in order to set clear objectives and roadmaps that are in line with other major EU legislations and agroecology.

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3. Policy brief n°2

10 Steps to Achieve the European Green Deal

The European Green Deal is a monumental step in achieving a greener and more sustainable Europe, filled with promising targets which aim to culminate in *no net emissions of greenhouse gases by 2050* and *economic growth decoupled from resource use*. It establishes great potential for a fairer economy, the revitalisation of rural areas and sustainability. Yet, the roadmap on how to actualise such targets has yet to be realised.

This policy brief provides a roadmap, by giving recommendations for 10 concrete steps that can be taken to achieve the European Green Deal through agroecology, especially the Biodiversity and Farm to Fork Strategies. It will focus on many of the technical aspects, as well as on research, social responsibilities and responsible governance. Each step is to be considered as a whole, rather than individually, as many steps require the other in order to create true transformation.

Agroecology is a holistic concept that embraces a diversity of interpretations, intentions and realities, depending on the country and its context, history, stakeholders and socio-political environment. Its aim is to restructure the food system in a way that maximises ecological processes to attain sustainability – encompassing agricultural practices, science and social movements (Wezel et al., 2009). While it is dynamic and ever-changing, it holds at its heart sustainable agricultural practices that include: the use of local resources, enhancing soil health and life (improving organic matter and biological activity), increased use of legumes for nitrogen fixing qualities, agroecological infrastructures (habitats for biodiversity conservation and beneficial species for pest control), recycling biomass (optimising and closing nutrient cycles), reducing dependence on external synthetic inputs, enhancing diversity in crops and livestock, and increasing resilience against climate change. These all strengthen synergy between the various elements of the system that transform our local, regional, national and trans-national food systems on a large scale—economically, politically and socially.

(i) Strongly decrease synthetic pesticides and fertilisers

Farm to Fork Target: Reduce by 50 % the use and risk of chemical pesticides by 2030.

Agroecology uses natural cycles and ecological processes instead of relying on chemicals to achieve sustainable food. Rather than purchasing expensive inputs, it aims for a lower input

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agriculture that uses local resources, increases soil life and maintains nutrient flows at the farm and territorial level (e.g. through legumes and manure for nitrogen fixing qualities). By creating diverse and long crop rotations, intercropping, using a diversity of crops and keeping constant soil cover, it creates a synergetic system that halts the pest and weed reproduction cycles and makes pesticides (insecticides, herbicides, fungicides) obsolete. It simultaneously minimises resource losses (water, nutrients, biomass). The focus in such a system is transformed from maximum yields to optimum yields, while also diminishing dependence on global trade.

Farm to Fork Target: Reduce fertiliser use by at least 20 % by 2030.

The reduction of pesticides is often automatically linked with the reduction of synthetic fertiliser use since plant varieties whose great yield is only possible with growth regulators and pesticides are no longer used. This can be achieved through the fertilisation that occurs through symbiotic fixation from leguminous crops and through nitrogen transfers from livestock, especially ruminants. These two systems should not be seen individually but in symbiosis as both are important tools to ensure human and environmental health (e.g. eutrophication, emissions), and keeps us within planetary boundaries.

(ii) Increase mixed crop-livestock systems

Farm to Fork Target: Reduce nutrient losses by at least 50 % while ensuring no deterioration on soil fertility

One of the most important components of agroecological transformation is returning fertility to soils and valuing the innumerable services of soil organisms. Within agroecology, animals are vital to soil fertility, especially when livestock and crop production is reconnected in mixed crop-livestock systems. Such integrated systems either grow animals and crops on a single farm, or cooperate amongst neighbouring farms for the exchange of hay, straw and manure, creating regional autonomy. This is optimal for the reduction of fertilisers and nutrient losses, as animal manure can increase soil fertility on the spot or through nitrogen transfers, which additionally reduces animal waste, transport emissions related to feed and imported deforestation (which hurts global biodiversity and increases GHG emissions). The integration of crops and animals on a single farm, while sharing space at the same time or in rotation, creates deep interactions which provide environmental services and social benefits (e.g. economic resilience). Further, a regional system founded on a mosaic of diverse landscape structures creates an equilibrium for both crops and livestock needs.

(iii) Enhance animal health and extensively manage livestock

Target: Reduce sales of antimicrobials for farmed animals and in aquaculture by 50 % by 2030.

Within intensive conventional agriculture, animals are often kept indoors in conditions that not only increase diseases but cause severe animal welfare issues related to discomfort, pain, fear, distress, and abnormal behaviours. Extensively managed, grass-based livestock systems on the other hand, halt almost all of these concerns simply by animals living outside, giving them access to healthier feed provisioning and conditions. When a farmer includes rotational grazing and crop-livestock rotations, intestinal parasites can be managed through the disruption of the host-pathogen cycles and herbal leys can be incorporated to regulate animal health without veterinary drugs. This change would also revitalise and maintain grasslands, increase biodiversity within grasslands, and should include diverse animal breeds that easily digest woody fodder, are more suited to local realities (i.e. climate, terrain), and are ‘dual purpose’ for both meat and milk. Such systems would prioritise breeds for their performance criteria from quantity of milk or meat, to their ability to adapt to a changing climate. Further, the mineral makeup of milk and meat from such systems also changes to create healthier diets with Omega-3 content of milk doubled when animals are feeding on grass which is critical for cardiovascular health in humans (IDDRI, 2018). Lastly, extensively managed systems give priority to crops directly consumed by humans as they are no longer in competition with feed, which is often imported from great distances with high GHG emissions, creating a more autonomous Europe.

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(iv) Restore and enlarge permanent grasslands

Biodiversity Strategy Target: Strictly protect at least a third of the EU’s protected areas - representing 10% of the EU land and 10% of EU sea - including all remaining primary and old-growth forests as well as other carbon rich ecosystems, such as peatlands, grasslands, wetlands, mangroves and seagrass meadows.

The restoration of Europe’s grasslands is not only important for their immense carbon sink qualities (can store up to 30% of the world’s carbon) but they are also the heart of European biodiversity (up to 79 species in just 1 m² in Europe)(IDDRI, 2018). Therefore, addressing biodiversity loss cannot be done without a focus on grasslands, which often include important agroecological infrastructure (hedges, wood clumps, grass strips, ponds, ditches) which provide food, shelter, and ecological and territorial connectivity. For biodiversity purposes it

is important to focus on extensively managed permanent grassland to provide a continuity of landscape and habitats for reproduction, as tilled or fertilised grasslands lose species richness. Further, the conservation of diversified grasslands implies the support of the livestock systems which ensure their vitality, keeping traditional diets in a way that does not impact the planet.

(v) Return trees to agricultural landscapes

Biodiversity Strategy Target: Plant 3 billion trees by 2030.

Increasing tree cover is important for many reasons, including to combat climate change, increase biodiversity and for animal welfare, but how and where those trees are planted is of utmost importance. If trees are planted in commercial monocultural forestry systems, the benefits derived from them, beyond carbon sequestration, are very limited. Similarly, large-scale tree planting in grassland areas where diversity is already very high would be counterproductive. Therefore, it is important that trees are planted to support and regenerate already functioning agroecosystems. The European Green Deal could use agroforestry to accomplish such a target, as agroforestry is a multifunctional land use approach that delivers environmental, social and economic benefits that can be used at any scale, by all farmers, including small-scale farmers. The benefits of agroecological agroforestry systems are many: they control pests; improve soil fertility, water quality, and biodiversity; reduce erosion; sequester carbon; capture excess nitrogen; create buffers in storms and droughts; ensure ecological corridors and generate diversified incomes. Most importantly, agroforestry provides both economic and environmental resilience where disturbances and extreme weather events will continue to cause instability in coming years.

(vi) Diversify the types and number of crops grown on a single farm

Green Deal Target: The EU's goals are to reduce the environmental and climate footprint of the EU food system and strengthen its resilience, ensure food security in the face of climate change and biodiversity loss and lead a global transition towards competitive sustainability from farm to fork and tapping into new opportunities.

Increasing the diversity and number of crops grown on a single farm is necessary in order to create environmental and economic resilience to a changing climate which incorporates the use of annual, perennial and permanent crops. This includes variety in space and time, using a mix of practices that include intercropping, diversified rotations, agroforestry, and crop diversification at the farm scale. Such complexities can be used to provide economic (e.g.

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multiple incomes in case of pest outbreaks) and environmental tools (e.g. drought resistant varieties, resilience to climate change). It can also support healthy, diverse and culturally appropriate diets which respect food traditions. New crops, rarely used crop species, and locally adapted breeds and crops are important pillars for climate adaptation. It is important to mention that this does not mean the production of genetically modified seeds which seek to create a single variety of each crop that relies on synthetic inputs, instead of increasing system diversity. Further, the ability to save a seed, which is not possible with GMO crops, creates not only autonomy for the farmer, it is also a vital tool for climate mitigation as season after season, specific attributes are bred into the seed naturally, with the needs of that particular region. The heart of crop diversity is also the ability for communities to engage in food sovereignty and seed exchange, which preserves intergenerational land practices and cultural meaning.

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(vii) Increase diversity of habitats

Biodiversity Strategy Target: Bring back at least 10% of agricultural area under high diversity landscape features by 2030.

Increased diversity in plant and animal species ensures the sustainability and well functioning of that particular ecosystem, including the pollinators agriculture and human diets strongly rely on. Yet diversity is not only important within fauna and flora, but also within habitats. Within agroecology, mosaics of different landscapes in different forms and sizes, that serve both humans and non-human members of the environment, are fundamental. This includes forests, arable land, and grassland with agroecological infrastructure of hedges, woody clumps, grass strips, ponds, and ditches all within close proximity. These habitats and their functional biodiversity regulate any insect or plant from becoming a pest, providing essential ecosystem services for agricultural production, as well as ecological corridors.

(viii) Increase the adoption of organic farming

Farm to Fork Target: Achieve 25 % of total farmland under organic farming by 2030.

Organic farming, in its most rigorous form, includes many agroecological practices for closed loop, ecologically sound systems that provide dignified incomes for farmers, as well as the preservation of family farming, which is responsible for over half of all food production in Europe (Eurostat, 2020). Organic farming calls for alternatives to pesticides, veterinary products, non-synthetic crop fertilisers, as well as higher animal welfare. Although organic

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farming is not (yet) focused on the more social aspects that are demanded in agroecological food systems, it has a focus on environmental degradation and human health that can help preserve natural resources, encourage biodiversity both inside the farm and in surrounding areas, sequester carbon, ensure soil health and eliminate many of the emissions and toxic repercussions of synthetic pesticides and fertilisers.

(ix) Increase research on best practices at the local and regional scale for all aspects of the food system including for climate, soil, land management, and crop and animal diversity

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Biodiversity Strategy Target: 10 billion euros under Horizon Europe [are] to be invested in R&I related to food, bioeconomy, natural resources, agriculture, fisheries, aquaculture and environment.

Research and innovation are key drivers in the agroecological transition to sustainable and healthy food systems. In order to ensure resilience under a changing climate, and to become less dependent on fossil fuel based global trade, it is important to invest in research that can provide farmers with state of the art data that is specific to their climates, terrains and realities. One of agroecology's fundamental pillars is focusing on the local and regional scale, creating strategies that are diverse in each farm and region, rather than a one-size-fits-all solution. Such research can go beyond the academic halls of Europe's universities and include the establishment of networks of living labs and EU partnerships that focus on agroecology, food and soil. An enabling framework to bring these ambitions to life will need to bridge many sectors such as finance, capacity, research, innovation and technology in order to provide systems-based research that moves away from quick fixes and silver-bullet solutions. Such research needs to be disseminated and paired with knowledge exchange and training that is farmer to farmer led. The AE4EU project has taken the first steps on many of these tasks, first by mapping agroecology across European countries to give an overview of the different realities of agroecology thus far, encompassing subjects such as living labs, science and research, education and training, social movements, as well as in practice. Through this initial mapping it was found that in order to improve the strength of the living lab concept, an important tool for agroecological transformation, it is important for each region to provide their own diffusion of the term and adjust it according to local realities. Next, the project will create a hub, a virtual space where individuals from all related professions can gather information and share knowledge, practices and experiences. The hub aims to be a space of

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connection for farmers, researchers, students, chefs, professors, citizens, social movements, NGO's and policy makers.

(x) Promote participatory and multi-stakeholder approaches in knowledge generation

Green Deal Target: Reduce net emissions of greenhouse gases by at least 55% by 2030.

The EU has pledged to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and become climate neutral by 2050. This requires research and innovation by a variety of stakeholders in a participatory and co-creative process that is people-led, inclusive, transdisciplinary and holistic. AE4EU is engaging in such a process through the creation of a network of networks that aims to complement, support and link existing groups, initiatives and programmes that are working towards the development of agroecology. This network is led by 30 different organisations, mostly outside of the Horizon 2020 project, and will continue to exist once the project has ended. By enabling participation across all sectors, innovative solutions can be created that are rooted in equality and a just transition. This includes relinquishing power imbalances in the food system by treating uniformly all diverse ways of knowing, including traditional knowledge, lived experience, case studies and observations, to complement scientific data (Global Alliance for the Future of Food, 2021). In order to achieve climate neutrality, it is important to redesign our food system completely in a way that goes beyond production and focuses on socio-economic aspects such as responsible governance and re-establishing connections between growers and those who eat. Further, it is vital that short and long term considerations are included in all future decision-making for thoughtful transformation which addresses systemic issues and creates system-wide benefits.

The way forward

The European Commission has done significant work to create strategies that will enable a just and sustainable transition for Europe through the Green Deal. Yet, the lack of frameworks to guide such a shift in agricultural production especially, has meant that the path has not yet gained critical momentum. AE4EU has created such a framework that although concrete, can be redefined to the local scale. This framework is characterised by a mosaic of different systems, landscapes and practices that are rooted in regionality and respect cultural traditions. Each member state can continue this work by creating their own policies tailored to their country's context and conditions which are guided by these 10 steps, while keeping in mind HLPE's 13 principles of agroecology, both in their state policies and through their CAP Strategic Plans, especially through the eco-schemes, which AE4EU has written another policy brief with even more specific guidance.

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Reference List

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4. Conclusion

In conclusion, these policy briefs are meant to provide guidelines and roadmaps into the future of agriculture, and more specifically into the agroecological transition. They show that agroecology is not a wish list of best practices, but a concrete roadmap to achieve all of the goals set out in the agricultural legislations of the European Union. This is especially true in crisis situations where ‘business as usual’ is disrupted in events such as the war in Ukraine or Covid-19. Transition to agroecology can represent a more autonomous Europe that is resilient to any shocks that may occur in the future. These briefs are not exhaustive but do provide clear pillars for policy makers, civil society and academics to base their future work on.

5. Impact Evaluation

In accordance with the proposal, two policy briefs were developed and disseminated respectively in February 2022 (policy brief on Eco-schemes) and June 2022 (policy brief on the European Green Deal) 2022. Both are¹ disseminated through the AE4EU website as well as the network of AE4EU partners – especially through the activities of Agroecology Europe, a partner of AE4EU. The first policy brief was disseminated widely, including the SCAR Agroecology group which prepares the European partnership in Agroecology living labs and research infrastructures. Further, it was published on other websites, such as the FAO’s Agroecology Knowledge Hub, and used as a policy tool in one of Agroecology Europe’s policy workshops in Brussels in February 2022 which gathered both policy makers from DG AGRI, DG ENVI and representatives of the EU parliament, and a springboard for discussions both within and outside of the project. The second policy brief was released shortly before the summer holiday and therefore has not had as wide of dissemination. Nevertheless, it has been published both on the AE4EU and AEEU websites. The project is planning on engaging in further dissemination of this brief during the fall season, including within events and newsletters.

¹ <https://www.ae4eu.eu/ae4eu-policy-brief/>